

Contextualizing and Connecting Collections of Letters

Workshop DH Benelux 2025

Chair: Maria Eskevich

Co-organizers: Judith Brouwer, Bente Frissen, Juliette Huygen

Workshop Program

- Introduction of the day
- *PICA Verkennen*: CEN 2.0 by Judith Brouwer (Huygens & Meertens Institute)
- Keynote: CLARIN Perspective on metadata by Dieter Uytvanck (CLARIN)

11:00 – 11:15 Coffee Break

- Metadata and vocabularies: Judith Brouwer and Mari Wigham (Huygens Institute)

12:30 – 14:00 Lunch

- Data enrichments within letters – contextualizing entities: Nina Lamal and Marijn Koolen (Huygens Institute)

15:15 – 15:30 Coffee Break

- Data collection crossovers: Juliette Huijgen (Huygens Institute)
- Discussion and wrap-up

Introduction of the day

Bente Frissen

Introduction of the day

Huygens Institute of Dutch history and culture

- > 200 online resources
- > **150.000 letters**

Recently launched resources

- Goetgevonden.nl
- Mondrian Papers
- Correspondence of Christofforo Suriano

Introduction of the day

Last year

- *Making Scholarly Collections of Letters Insightful and Accessible for a Wider Audience.*
- Heterogeneity in collections
- Contextualizing data to reach the audience

Today

- Werk aan Uitvoering and Access to Context: data-envelopes
- Goetgevonden.nl and Suriano Letters: annotating entities
- Van Gogh Letters and Mondrian Papers: connecting collections

***PICA Verkennen* grant: CEN 2.0 ~ historical letters**

Contextualizing and Connecting Collections of Letters (CCCL)
DH Benelux 2025

Judith Brouwer
3 June 2025

CEN: Catalogus Epistularum Neerlandicarum

LETTER DATABASE hosted by the KB, the National Library of the Netherlands:

- **585,000** descriptions of individual letters and parts of correspondences
- written in the **(early-)modern period** (ca. 1500 - present)
- information about **more than two million** letters
- from the collections of **Dutch heritage institutions**, for example
 - the KB,
 - the Museum of Literature
 - Amsterdam, Utrecht and Leiden University Libraries

Gerard ter Borch, *De briefschrijfster* (ca. 1655), Mauritshuis Den Haag, inv.nr. 797

CEN: Catalogus Epistularum Neerlandicarum

Zoeken | Resultaten | Geavanceerd | Mijn archief | Mijn instellingen | Help

zoeken [en] Afzender (brs) sorteer op relevantie

zoeken minder

Thesaurus ingangen Publicaties Beide

Catalogus Epistularum Neerlandicarum

De CEN is een catalogus van de tot op heden ontsloten brieven berustend in de collecties van samenwerkende N correspondentiedelen geschreven in de vroegmoderne en moderne tijd (ca. 1500 - heden). Daarmee verschaft de

De Catalogus Epistularum Neerlandicarum wordt samengesteld en uitgegeven door:
CEN
p/a Koninklijke Bibliotheek
Postbus 90407
2509 LK 's-Gravenhage

<https://webggc.oclc.org/cbs/DB=3.23/>

Zoeken | Resultaten | Geavanceerd | Mijn archief | Mijn instellingen | Help

zoeken [en] Afzender (brs) sorteer op

Thesaurus inga

Catalogus Epistularu

De CEN is een catalogo even berus
correspondentiedelen g moderne tij

De Catalogus Epistular steld en uit
CEN
p/a Koninklijke Bibliotheek
Postbus 90407
2509 LK 's-Gravenhage

- Afzender (brs)
- Ontvanger (bro)
- Corporatie afzender (cos)
- Corporatie ontvanger (coo)
- Titelwoorden (ttl)
- Alle woorden (all)
- Persoonsnaam (pao)
- Plaats van verzending (pls)
- Taalcode (taa)
- Update datum (upd)
- Bewaarplaats en signatuur (bsg)
- Beroepsaanduiding (brp)

2026: end of CEN

- The CEN will be **phased out** in '26
- Several institutions moved to WorldCat
 - They **stopped cataloguing** their collections in the **GGC system** (Gemeenschappelijk Geautomatiseerd Catalogiseersysteem) which had previously been used to **prepare metadata for the CEN**
 - Worldcat itself **can't replace CEN**; it can't:
 - **distinguish individual letters** in a collection
 - record **essential correspondence metadata**

Example: 4 letters/poems by painter, poet, classical scholar [etc.] Anna Maria van Schurman

@ CEN 1.0

titellijst	titelgegevens	zoekgeschiedenis	eerste
resultaten zoeken [en] (Afzender (brs)) schurman 50 treffers			

bewaren

Leiden, UB : HUG 37

Titel: Brieven van Anna Maria van **Schurman** (1607-1678) aan Constantijn Huygens (1596-1687)

Afzender: Anna Maria van **Schurman** (1607-1678) (ISNI 0000 0001 1644 8828)

Ontvanger: Constantijn Huygens (1596-1687) (ISNI 0000 0001 0870 8781)

Jaar: 1649-1658

Taal: lat

Aantal: 4 br

Annotatie: gedichten als brief verzonden.

universiteit leiden

Signatuur: HUG 37

8 (9)
metadata
fields

perma

<https://webggc.oclc.org/cbs/DB=3.23/XMLPRS=Y/PPN?PPN=850161215>

Jan Lievens - Portrait of Anna Maria van Schurman (1649) National Gallery, London, NG1095

Michiel Jansz. van Mierevelt, Constantijn Huygens (1596-1687) (1641), Huygens-museum Hofwijck, Voorburg

@ Catalogue University Library Leiden

LETTER ←

Brieven van Anna Maria van Schurman (1607-1678) aan Constantijn Huygens (1596-1687)., HUG 37

Schurman, Anna Maria van, 1607-1678, ;
1649-1658

Available at Special Collections Reading Room Letters (HUG 37) >

Details	
Title	Brieven van Anna Maria van Schurman (1607-1678) aan Constantijn Huygens (1596-1687).
Author/Creator	Schurman, Anna Maria van, 1607-1678, > Recipient : Huygens, Constantijn, 1596-1687 >
Shelfmark	HUG 37
Date	1649-1658
Form	4
Language	Latin
Description	Note : gedichten als brief verzonden.
Identifier	This item in WorldCat : 798338749

10 metadata fields

derwerpen Lijsten Over Voor bibliothecarissen

Brieven van Anna Maria van Schurman (1607-1678) aan Constantijn Huygens (1596-1687) HUG 37

Auteurs: [Constantijn Huygens](#) (Geadresseerde)
Meer tonen... ▾

 Manuscript, Latijn, 1649-1658

Fysieke beschrijving:	4 br.
OCLC-nummer / uniek kenmerk:	798338749
Opmerkingen:	gedichten als brief verzonden
Opmerkingen gebeurtenis:	Brieven niet gedateerd maar met ontvangstdata genoteerd door ontvanger.

7 metadata fields, but...

2026: end of CEN

Huge step back!

- *PICA Verkennen* grant ~ 'Towards a new letter portal' (2024-2025)
 - Workshops/meetings with CEN's main data suppliers
- Resulted in:
 1. a technical **implementation plan**;
 2. a sustainability **strategy for a national/overarching *Brievenportaal*** to replace the CEN
- Next phase = apply for *PICA Verbinden* grant (Oct. '25) ➡ **metadata agreements/data suppliers**
- DHB '26!

Keynote presentation

Dieter Uytvanck
CLARIN

Session Metadata and vocabularies

Metadata of the Meertens Institute Collections

Judith Brouwer

The Meertens Institute

- **What?** ‘... studies and documents **language and culture in the Netherlands**, and Dutch language and culture throughout the world. We focus on the phenomena that shape everyday life in society.’ <https://meertens.knaw.nl/>
- **Research projects:**
 - Makebelief: how religion is presented in **religious theme parks** in different countries;
 - Odeuropa: the **role of smells** in European culture and history
 - Inreach: **missing knowledge and perspectives** @ Meertens archives
- **Collections:**
 - >70.000 books
 - >180 digital & >500 paper collections
 - thousands of hours of audio-recordings

Metadating the MI Collections: Dublin Core

BACKGROUND DUBLIN CORE

- **What?**
 - A *standard* (metadata vocabulary) for describing resources of any type
- **When & where?**
 - 1985: conference with metadata- and webspecialists @ OCLC*-headquarters in Dublin, Ohio (US)
 - *Online Computer Library Center - WorldCat
- **Why?**
 - Goal = to create a brief *description* using a number of *attributes* to make *metadata* on resources *better exchangeable*

Core elements - metadata

- 1) Title
- 2) DC Creator
- 3) Subject [*ELSST: European Language Social Science Thesaurus*]
- 4) Description
- 5) DC Date created
- 6) Access rights
- 7) Contributor
- 8) Spatial coverage

- 9) Temporal coverage
- 10) Source
- 11) Identifier
- 12) Format
- 13) Relation
- 14) Language
- 15) Remarks
- 16) Publisher
- 17) Licence

Example: nr. 1050 Collectie Brieven aan de toekomst (Collection Letters to the future)

Dublin Core

DC Creator Meertens Instituut

Title Collectie Brieven aan de Toekomst (BadT). 1998 (2015)

Description De collectie is digitaal en bestaat uit digitale versies van ca. 15 brieven uit het Brieven aan de Toekomst-project (zie onder), met in enkele gevallen bijbehorende documentatie. De brieven zijn gekopieerd van 3½-inch diskettes. De bestandnamen corresponderen met de nummers van de brieven in het papieren archief. De collectie bevat ook twee audiobestanden met een lied ter promotie van het project.

Voor de papieren collectie, zie: collectienr. 198

Voor de audiocollectie, zie: collectienr. 2041

Brieven aan de Toekomst:

DC Date created 07-04-2015

Access rights Restricted Acces

Contributor Het Nederlands Centrum van Volkscultuur (Utrecht). het

Subject GESCHIEDENIS. DAGELIJKS LEVEN. DAGBOEKEN.

Spatial coverage Nederland (<http://vocab.aetv.edu/page/tan/7016845>)

Temporal coverage 15-05-1998

Source n.v.t.

Identifier <https://hdl.handle.net/10744/7b9319d8-6d8a-49bc-be63>

Format doc. txt. .eml. ipa

Relation Ad de Jong en Carla Wiers (redactie). met medewerking

Language nld

Remarks Reden Restricted Access: AVG.

De inhoud van deze collectie valt binnen niveau 5 (legally sensitive, restricted) van het HuC data classification-model uit 2024.

Publisher Meertens Instituut

Licence CC BY-NC

Further metadating activities @ Meertens & Huygens

- ❑ 1 project to **improve the accessibility and quality** of the digital Meertens Collections (Julie Peterse)
 - ❑ Future project: same for the paper collections (more metadata)
- ❑ 1 project on **joint datamanagement**
- ❑ Further collaboration 2 institutes:
 - mapping Dublin Core & Data Envelopes

Data-Envelopes

Mari Wigham

Session Data enrichments within letters – contextualizing entities

Suriano Letters

Nina Lamal

Goetgevonden.nl

Marijn Koolen

Session Collection crossovers & creative activations

Juliette Huijgen

Vincent van Gogh

The Letters

by period
by correspondent
by place
with sketches

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[Book edition](#)

Edited by Leo Jansen, Hans Luijten and Nienke Bakker

The letters are the window to Van Gogh's universe.

This edition, the product of 15 years of research at the Van Gogh Museum and Huygens ING, contains all Van Gogh's letters to his brother Theo, his artist friends Paul Gauguin and Emile Bernard, and many others.

Here you will find the letters in the latest edition (2009), richly annotated and illustrated, with new transcriptions and authorized English translations.

[Quick Guide >>>](#)

Book edition

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The Mondrian Papers

The complete letters and theoretical writings of Piet Mondrian

Now available: letters and writings up to July 1919

Edited by Wietse Coppes and Leo Jansen

Technical Consultant: Peter Boot

Website Development: Gijsjan Brouwer / ruimdetijd.nl

Latest update: 12 March 2024

Search the edition

Published by

Huygens Institute for the History and Culture of the Netherlands (KNAW)

RKD – Netherlands Institute for Art History

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The Mondrian Papers is an academic online edition of the entire correspondence and theoretical writings of the Dutch artist Piet Mondrian (1872-1944). The edition will be fully annotated and illustrated. All relevant secondary sources (personal documents, studio and portrait photos, amongst others) are also included in the edition.

The Mondrian Papers is a work in progress and will be published in parts. This site will keep you updated on the developments whilst also offering information on the background of the Mondrian Edition Project, of which *The Mondrian Papers* is the result.

The site also regularly lists project news (see [News](#)) and information about a number of projects which have a direct link to *The Mondrian Papers* (see [More](#)).

The Mondrian Edition Project is a collaboration between the [RKD – Netherlands Institute for Art History](#) and the [Huygens Institute for History and Culture of the Netherlands \(KNAW\)](#) (see [Organisation](#)).

Podcast Van Goghs mooiste brieven

Nederlandse schrijvers, acteurs en muzikanten lezen voor uit de beroemde brieven van Vincent van Gogh en vertellen wat haar of hem persoonlijk raakt.

h

A Boat

Vervaardiger
Dirk Nijland

Vervaardigingsdatum
1927

Identificatie
49696

Soort object
Werken op papier

Dataprovieder
Kröller-Müller Museum

Materiaal
paper (letter)
papier (brief)

Gebruiksrecht
<http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/nc/1.0/>

Uitgebreide informatie

A certain ennui is always with me, and when I forget my sorrow for a moment it's because I've had a drink.

Letters between Paul Cézanne and Émile Zola
Paul Cézanne, 1860

Censor sentences

- War changes
- War never changes

Dear Daddy,

I hope you are not alarmed, you should not be. Unlike the past few months, these days the front is calm, the weather is nice and we have food and water. _____

_____ They told us that we will have a small truce this summer for Mary's Heavenly ascension. I really just want to come back home and hug you all.

Yours, Albert

SEND

Notes

LETTERS FROM THE WAR

ALL REVIEWS: [Positive \(40\)](#)

RELEASE DATE: 24 Jan, 2025

DEVELOPER: [Etrurian Games](#)

PUBLISHER: [Etrurian Games](#)

Popular user-defined tags for this product:

[Adventure](#) [Text-Based](#) [Pixel Graphics](#) [Historical](#) +

A Membership For People Who *Really* Love History.

Get weekly "snail mail" from George Washington, Theodore Roosevelt, Marie Curie, and other legendary figures.

Pick Your Topic

Early American Handwriting

Purpose

Handwritten colonial documents provide a wealth of information. For colonists, the way a person wrote conveyed not only social status, but also revealed one's gender and occupation.

The goal of this game is to decode the **explicit** messages of handwritten documents. You will learn to recognize some commonly confused letters. When you are done with this game visit the [Early Printing & Handwriting Collection](#) to practice reading longer passages from colonial manuscripts and learn more about the implicit messages colonists were sending.

Instructions

To practice identifying individual letters, begin the game and then click a manuscript letter*. Next, click the print letter to which you believe it corresponds. To see the answers for all the letters click on ANSWERS at the top of the screen. Click START to begin!

START

* Manuscript letters used with permission from: Reading early American handwriting, by Kip Sperry Baltimore, Md.: Genealogical Pub. Co., c1998

published here

